

3D THERMAL BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE PLATES USING FINITE LAYER METHOD

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SUMMARY

The finite layer method is applied to 3D thermal buckling analysis of antisymmetric angle-ply piezoelectric composite plates. The effects of material properties and structural geometry are investigated and the results are compared with available solutions.

Keywords: Finite layer method, 3D thermal buckling analysis, antisymmetric angle-ply laminate, piezoelectric layer, smart structures

INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric composite plates composed of piezoelectric layers and fibre-reinforced plastic layers constitute an important element of smart structures. These structures are often exposed to high temperature environments. As the temperature rises, thermal stresses in the structure build up. When the thermal stresses increase to a certain level, the structure may lose its elastic stability and thermal buckling occurs. Several research works have been conducted to investigate the thermal buckling behaviours of smart composite plates (see for example [1 to 3]). However, most of the published results are approximate solutions obtained by means of simplified two-dimensional models according to a variety of plate theories with varied complexities. Therefore, whenever possible, three dimensional solutions are desirable in order to investigate the performance of such structures more accurately. This is especially important for the relatively thick plates. The obtained results will provide important information, which can not be extracted from two-dimensional analysis, and the solutions will also be useful for verification of other analysis tools such as a new plate theory and related numerical methods. In this context, Kapuria and Achary have recently published the exact 3D solution for thermal buckling of piezoelectric cross-ply laminates using state space approach, and important findings are presented [4]. However, to the authors' knowledge, the 3D thermal buckling analysis of piezoelectric angle-ply laminates has not been reported in any major international journal.

For simply supported rectangular plates, the finite layer method is the most efficient numerical method in the 3D analysis [5, 6]. In this method, each lamina in a composite

plate is modelled by one or more finite layers. Within each finite layer, the trigonometric functions are used for the inplane interpolations of displacements, whereas the polynomials are employed for the interpolations in the thickness direction. Thus, the three dimensional analysis is transformed into a series of one dimensional analyses by virtue of the orthogonal properties of the trigonometric functions. Consequently, the results are more accurate than any analysis based on the plate theory since the solutions are true 3D solutions. On the other hand, the analysis is more efficient than 2D finite element analysis because the 3D analysis has been reduced to one-dimension. Recently, the present authors have conducted the finite layer thermal buckling analysis of piezoelectric cross-ply laminates, yielding satisfactory accuracy and efficiency [6].

In the present study, the finite layer method is extended to the 3D thermal buckling analysis of simply supported rectangular piezoelectric antisymmetric angle-ply laminates. The laminate may also include some symmetrical cross-ply. The present analysis takes into account the full coupling between the thermal, electrical and mechanical fields [3, 7], whereas the material properties are assumed to be independent of both the temperature and the electric field. In addition, the pre-buckling state of the plate is assumed to be steady. Therefore, temperature distribution in the plate is independently determined based on the equation of heat conduction; and the associated thermal stresses are computed accordingly. Then, the geometrical stiffness matrix is formed in the same way as in the elastic three-dimensional buckling analysis [5]. The critical temperature rise and the buckling mode can be obtained by solving related matrix equations.

Numerical results are presented to verify the proposed method. The effects of material properties and structural geometry are investigated.

COUPLED THERMAL, ELECTRICAL, MECHANICAL FIELDS

For the materials with fully coupled thermal, electrical and mechanical fields, the constitutive equations can be given in the tensor notion as [3, 7]:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{kl} - e_{ijk}E_k - \beta_{ij}\theta \quad (1)$$

$$D_i = e_{ijk}\varepsilon_{jk} + \eta_{ij}E_j + p_i\theta \quad (2)$$

$$S = \beta_{ij}\varepsilon_{ij} + p_iE_i + \frac{\rho c_v}{T_0}\theta \quad (3)$$

where σ_{ij} and ε_{ij} are respectively the components of the stress tensor and strain tensor, D_i and E_i are respectively the components of electric displacement vector and electric field vector, S is the entropy, and θ is the temperature rise from the initial temperature T_0 . The coefficients C_{ijkl} , e_{ijk} and η_{ij} denote respectively the elastic constants, the piezoelectric constants and the dielectric permittivity. The quantities β_{ij} and p_i refer respectively to the stress-temperature expansion coefficients and pyroelectric constants,

whereas ρ and c_v respectively represent the mass density and the specific heat per unit mass at constant strain.

The strain components ε_{ij} have the following relationships with the displacement components u_i :

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) + \frac{1}{2}u_{k,i}u_{k,j} \quad (4)$$

whereas the electric fields are related to the electrostatic potential ϕ as

$$E_i = -\phi_{,i} \quad (5)$$

In addition, the solution of a steady-state problem should satisfy the following variational equations to maintain the equilibrium of stresses, charges and heat, respectively:

$$\int_V \sigma_{ij} \delta \varepsilon_{ij} dV = \int_A t_i \delta u_i dA \quad (6)$$

$$\int_V D_i \delta \phi_{,i} dV = \int_A D_n \delta \phi dA \quad (7)$$

$$\int_V \kappa_{ij} \theta_{,i} \delta \theta_{,j} dV = \int_A q_n \delta \theta dA \quad (8)$$

where t_i and q_n denote the applied surface traction and heat flux, respectively, V and A respectively stand for the volume and surface area of the considered domain, whereas κ_{ij} represents the thermal conductivity. For a steady-state problem, the temperature distribution can be determined from Equation (8) independently, and Equation (3) is not required in the corresponding solution procedure [8].

PRE-BUCKLING SOLUTION

A uniform temperature rise T is considered in the present study in order to simplify comparison with other solutions. A set of uniform actuation potentials $\phi^\circ(z_k)$ may also be applied to the surfaces $z = z_k$ of piezoelectric layers. In addition, it is assumed that the plate remains flat without any out-of-plane bending and the inplane displacements remain zero as these loads increase proportionally until buckling occurs [4, 9]. For antisymmetric angle-ply laminates combined with symmetrical cross-ply and piezoelectric layers poling along the thickness direction z , it can be verified that the above loads only yield inplane stresses σ_x° , σ_y° , τ_{xy}° , strain ε_z° and electric field E_z° , which all remain constant within each layer, whereas all other state components are equal to zero. Thus, the initial inplane stresses in each layer can be determined from the constitutive equations in the x-y-z system:

$$\sigma_x^\circ = \bar{Q}_{13} \varepsilon_z^\circ - \bar{e}_{31} E_z^\circ - \beta_{xx} T \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_y^\circ = \bar{Q}_{23} \varepsilon_z^\circ - \bar{e}_{32} E_z^\circ - \beta_{yy} T \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^\circ = \bar{Q}_{63} \varepsilon_z^\circ - \bar{e}_{36} E_z^\circ - \beta_{xy} T \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_z^\circ = \bar{Q}_{33} \varepsilon_z^\circ - \bar{e}_{33} E_z^\circ - \beta_{zz} T = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$D_z^\circ = \bar{e}_{33}\varepsilon_z^\circ + \eta_{zz}E_z^\circ + p_3T \quad (13)$$

where \bar{Q}_{ij} are the elastic moduli, \bar{e}_{ij} are the piezoelectric moduli, β_{xx} , β_{yy} , β_{xy} and β_{zz} are the stress-temperature expansion coefficients, η_{zz} is the dielectric permittivity, p_3 is the pyroelectric constant, the superscript $^\circ$ represents the pre-buckling state, and $E_z^\circ = -\Delta\phi^\circ/t$ with t denoting the thickness of piezoelectric layer, and $\Delta\phi^\circ$ denoting the increment of ϕ° across the layer.

For an actuator layer, the electrical field E_z° is given. Therefore, σ_x° , σ_y° and τ_{xy}° can be directly calculated by means of Equations (9) to (11), after the value of ε_z° is obtained from Equation (12).

For a sensor layer, D_z° is equal to zero. Thus, ε_z° and E_z° can be obtained using Equations (12) and (13). Then, σ_x° , σ_y° and τ_{xy}° are readily calculated from Equations (9) to (11).

Figure 1. A finite layer

FINITE LAYER METHOD FOR BUCKLING ANALYSIS

In the finite layer analysis of a piezoelectric composite plate, each material layer is modelled by one or more finite layers. Each finite layer has a number of equally spaced nodal planes, which are parallel to the plate middle plane $z = 0$, and labelled from the top to the bottom of the finite layer with $i = 1, 2, \dots$ (figure 1).

During a buckling process of a simply supported rectangular antisymmetric angle-ply laminate, the increments of generalized displacements at any point within a finite layer are expressed in terms of the respective nodal values using the following interpolations:

$$u = \sum_{m=1}^r \sum_{n=1}^s \sum_{i=1}^{nd} \left(\hat{u}_{mni} N_i(z) \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} + \tilde{u}_{mni} N_i(z) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \cos \frac{n\pi y}{b} \right)$$

$$v = \sum_{m=1}^r \sum_{n=1}^s \sum_{i=1}^{nd} \left(\hat{v}_{mni} N_i(z) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \cos \frac{n\pi y}{b} + \tilde{v}_{mni} N_i(z) \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \right)$$

$$w = \sum_{m=1}^r \sum_{n=1}^s \sum_{i=1}^{nd} \left(\hat{w}_{mni} N_i(z) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} + \tilde{w}_{mni} N_i(z) \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} \cos \frac{n\pi y}{b} \right)$$

$$\phi = \sum_{m=1}^r \sum_{n=1}^s \sum_{i=1}^{nd} \left(\hat{\phi}_{mni} N_i(z) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} + \tilde{\phi}_{mni} N_i(z) \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} \cos \frac{n\pi y}{b} \right) \quad (14)$$

where u , v , w denote incremental displacement components respectively in the x , y and z directions (figure 1), a and b are the side lengths of the plate in the x and y directions, respectively, ϕ refers to incremental electrostatic potential change, r and s are the numbers of series terms required in the analysis, nd is the selected number of nodal planes in a finite layer. $N_i(z)$ is the Lagrangian polynomial defined as:

$$N_i(z) = \prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^{nd} \frac{z - z_j}{z_i - z_j} \quad (15)$$

Using the above shape functions and calculated initial inplane stresses, the generalized stiffness matrix and geometrical stiffness matrix of the finite layer can be formed by following standard procedures commonly used in the finite element and finite layer analysis [3, 5, 6]. Then, the critical temperature rise and buckling mode can be determined by solving related matrix equations. If material properties and initial inplane stresses remain constant in the inplane directions, the different pairs of series terms become uncoupled by virtue of the orthogonal properties of the trigonometric functions [9]. Thus, the related matrix equations in the analysis can be formed and solved separately for each pair of series terms (m , n), so that the efficiency of the analysis is enhanced drastically.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

1. Thermal Buckling of 10-layer Square Antisymmetric Angle-Ply Laminates

The square antisymmetric angle-ply composite plate analyzed by Noor and Burton [9] is selected here to verify the proposed method. The plate has side length a , thickness h and 10 equally thick layers alternatively oriented at θ and $-\theta$ degrees from the x -axis. The four edges are simply supported with deflection and normal inplane displacement fixed on middle plane. The material properties are assumed as: $E_1 = 15 E_o$, $E_2 = E_3 = 1.0 E_o$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.5 E_o$, $G_{23} = 0.3356 E_o$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3$, $\nu_{23} = 0.49$, $\alpha_1 = 0.015 \alpha_o$, $\alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = 1.0 \alpha_o$, where E_o and α_o are the normalization factors respectively for the elastic moduli and the coefficients of thermal expansion.

In all the examples of this study, each lamina is modelled by one finite layer with four nodal layers. The resulting dimensionless critical temperature rise $\bar{T}_{cr} = \alpha_o T_{cr}$ and corresponding buckling mode (m , n) are listed in Table 1 as the function of θ and thickness-to-length ratio h/a . It can be seen that the present results are in close agreement with the exact 3D solutions of Noor and Burton [9].

2. Thermal Buckling of Square ($p/0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/p$) Piezoelectric Laminates

A square piezoelectric laminate analyzed by Kapuria and Achary [4] is reanalyzed here to further validate the proposed method. The laminate with side length a and thickness h consists of a ($0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$) sublaminates with four Graphite-Epoxy plies of $0.2h$ thickness each, and two continuous PZT-5A layers of thickness $0.1h$ each bonded to the

upper and lower surfaces of the sublaminate. The material properties are listed in Table 2. All four edges are simply supported with deflection and inplane displacements being fixed on the middle plane along each edge. Two sets of electrical condition are considered, namely the closed-circuit (CC) condition, where both the top and bottom surfaces of each piezoelectric layer are grounded with the electrical potential forced to remain zero, and the open-circuit (OC) condition, where only the inner surface of each piezoelectric layer is grounded, whereas the outer surface remains free.

The resulting dimensionless critical temperature rise $\bar{T}_{cr} = \alpha_o T_{cr} a^2 / h^2$ for $\alpha_o = 22.5 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ is given in Table 3. Results show that the proposed method yields excellent agreement with the exact 3D solutions of Kapuria and Achary [4].

Table 1. $\bar{T}_{cr} = \alpha_o T_{cr}$ of 10-layer square antisymmetric angle-ply ($\theta/-\theta\dots$) laminates

h/a	Method	$\theta = 0$ deg.	$\theta = 15$ deg.	$\theta = 30$ deg.	$\theta = 45$ deg.
0.01	Present	0.7463×10^{-3}	0.1115×10^{-2}	0.1502×10^{-2}	0.1674×10^{-2}
	Noor	0.7463×10^{-3}	0.1115×10^{-2}	0.1502×10^{-2}	0.1674×10^{-2}
0.10	Present	0.5769×10^{-1}	0.7888×10^{-1}	0.1099	0.1193
	Noor	0.5782×10^{-1}	0.7904×10^{-1}	0.1100	0.1194
0.30	Present	0.2045	0.2329		
	Noor	0.2057	0.2347		
(m, n)		(1, 2)	(1, 2)	(1, 1)	(1, 1)

3. Thermal Buckling of Square ($p/45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/p$) Laminates

The simply supported square ($p/45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/p$) laminate is analyzed to investigate the effects of piezoelectricity on its isothermal buckling behaviour under uniform temperature rise. The influence of the thermal-electrical coupling is also investigated through an assumed case, where the pyroelectric constant p_3 is set to 0. The dimensions, material properties and electric conditions of the laminate are identical to the previous example, whereas the displacement boundary conditions are the same as Example 1.

Table 2. Elastic, thermal and piezoelectric properties of piezoelectric laminates

<i>Properties</i>	<i>Graphite- Epoxy</i>	<i>PZT-5A</i>	<i>Properties</i>	<i>Graphite- Epoxy</i>	<i>PZT-5A</i>
E_1 (GPa)	181	61.0	ρ (kg/m^3)	1389	7600
E_2 (GPa)	10.3	61.0	c_v ($J/kg \cdot K$)	1409	420
E_3 (GPa)	10.3	53.2	d_{31} ($10^{-12} m/V$)	-	-171
G_{12} (GPa)	7.17	22.6	d_{32} ($10^{-12} m/V$)	-	-171
G_{23} (GPa)	2.87	21.1	d_{33} ($10^{-12} m/V$)	-	374
G_{31} (GPa)	7.17	21.1	d_{15} ($10^{-12} m/V$)	-	584
ν_{12}	0.28	0.35	d_{24} ($10^{-12} m/V$)	-	584
ν_{13}	0.28	0.38	η_{11} ($10^{-8} F/m$)	-	1.53
ν_{23}	0.33	0.38	η_{22} ($10^{-8} F/m$)	-	1.53
α_1 ($10^{-6}/K$)	0.02	1.5	η_{33} ($10^{-8} F/m$)	-	1.5
α_2 ($10^{-6}/K$)	22.5	1.5	p_3 ($C/m^2 \cdot K$)	-	0.0007
α_3 ($10^{-6}/K$)	22.5	2.0			

Table 3. $\bar{T}_{cr} = \alpha_o T_{cr} a^2 / h^2$ of square ($p/0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/p$) laminate

a/h	Closed-circuit condition		Open-circuit condition	
	Present	Kapuria	Present	Kapuria
5	6.9954	-	3.8430	-
10	11.721	11.721	6.6242	6.6242
100	15.604	15.604	9.0142	9.0143

The resulting dimensionless critical temperature rise $\bar{T}_{cr} = \alpha_o T_{cr} a^2 / h^2$ for $\alpha_o = 22.5 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ with buckling mode (1, 1) are shown in Table 4 and Figure 2 as the functions of the length-to-thickness ratio a/h . In addition, elastic solutions neglecting the piezoelectric effects are also listed in the table for comparison. Results show that the piezoelectric effect raises \bar{T}_{cr} slightly for the laminate under closed-circuit conditions, whereas \bar{T}_{cr} of the laminate under open-circuit conditions is significantly lower than the elastic solution. This is mainly attributed to the thermal-electrical coupling, i.e. the pyroelectric effect, which multiplies the pre-buckling stresses due to unit temperature rise as shown in Table 5, but has no contribution to the bending stiffness of the plate during the isothermal buckling process.

Table 4. Critical temperature rises $\bar{T}_{cr} = \alpha_o T_{cr} a^2 / h^2$ of square $(p/45^\circ / -45^\circ / 45^\circ / -45^\circ / p)$ laminate

a/h	CC	OC	OC & $p_3 = 0$	Elastic
5	7.485	4.077	7.390	7.478
10	13.418	7.487	13.526	13.411
100	18.730	10.666	19.207	18.723

Figure 2. Critical temperature rise of square $(p/45^\circ / -45^\circ / 45^\circ / -45^\circ / p)$ laminate.

Table 5. Pre-buckling stresses due to $\Delta T = 1^\circ K$ in ZPT-5A layer

Stresses	unit	CC	OC	OC & $p_3 = 0$	Elastic
$\sigma_x^\circ = \sigma_y^\circ$	MPa	0.1408	0.8295	0.1924	0.1408
E_z°	kV/m	0	-42.920	-3.2188	0

4. Effect of Angle θ° and Number of Layers

A simply supported square piezoelectric laminate with length-to-thickness ratio $a/h = 10$ consists of a sublaminates with even number of equal thick Graphite-Epoxy layers alternatively oriented at θ° and $-\theta^\circ$ from the x-axis. Two continuous PZT-5A layers of thickness $0.1h$ each are bonded to the upper and lower surfaces of the sublaminates. All other parameters, conditions and the analysis model are identical to the previous example. The resulting critical temperature rise $\bar{T}_{cr} = \alpha_o T_{cr} a^2 / h^2$ for $\alpha_o = 22.5 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ with buckling mode (1, 1) are shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that \bar{T}_{cr} reduces for the laminate with 2 sublaminates layers but rises for those with 4 and 8 sublaminates layers, as θ° increases from 0° to 45°

Figure 3. Effects of θ° on \bar{T}_{cr} for square ($p/\theta^\circ/-\theta^\circ/.../p$) laminate of $a/h=10$ under open-circuit condition (NSL = Number of Sublaminates Layers)

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the proposed finite layer method has been successfully applied to the 3D thermal buckling analysis of piezoelectric antisymmetric angle-ply laminates. The results are in reasonable agreement with published data. Numerical examples show that the piezoelectric laminate with open-circuits has significantly lower critical temperature rises than the elastic solutions, whereas the same laminate with closed-circuits has slightly higher critical temperature rises than the elastic solutions. Results also show that the critical temperature rise \bar{T}_{cr} increases with the number of layers. In addition, analysis indicates that \bar{T}_{cr} reduces for the laminate with 2 sublaminates but rises for those with 4 and 8 sublaminates, as θ° increases from 0° to 45° .

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